

Health Education Needs for Pregnant Women Attended PHCCs in Baghdad, Al-Russafa Health Directorate

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Abstract

Background: Prenatal health education is a key component of preventive care aimed at ensuring maternal and child health. Effective prenatal education raises awareness of health behaviors, encourages proper utilization of health services, and reduces disparities, particularly among vulnerable populations. The World Health Organization (WHO) recommends a minimum of four antenatal visits spaced throughout pregnancy, starting as early as possible in the first trimester. **Aim of the Study:** To assess the level of health awareness related to pregnancy. To identify the primary sources of information among pregnant women attending Primary Health Care Centers (PHCCs) in Baghdad Al-Russafa Health Directorate. **Patients & Methods:** A descriptive cross-sectional study was conducted in four PHCCs in Baghdad Al-Russafa from January to April 2014. Pregnant women, excluding primigravida in the first and second trimesters, were interviewed regarding socio-demographic, obstetric characteristics, PHC visits, antenatal procedures, and pregnancy-related awareness. **Results:** A total of 200 pregnant women participated; 91.0% lived in urban areas, and the mean age was 29.22 ± 6.31 years. Most (40.5%) had completed secondary education, and 48.0% attended PHCCs in the second trimester. Awareness of antenatal visits, necessary procedures, balanced diet, and physical activity was low. However, 82.5% were aware of smoking's effect on pregnancy, and 55.0% preferred more than two years between pregnancies. Main sources of health information were doctors, medical staff, mothers, and in-laws. **Conclusion:** While awareness was high regarding TT vaccine, folic acid intake, and birth spacing, knowledge gaps existed in antenatal care visit frequency, pregnancy investigations, postnatal care, and accepted exercises during pregnancy.

Introduction

Health education encompasses various learning experiences designed to enhance individuals' and communities' health by increasing knowledge and influencing attitudes [1]. Prenatal health education is a crucial preventive measure aimed at maintaining maternal and fetal health, ensuring normal delivery, and promoting childcare skills [2]. Globally, maternal mortality remains a critical issue, with over 500,000 maternal deaths annually due to pregnancy-related complications. Studies indicate that 88%-98% of these deaths could be prevented with proper management during pregnancy and labor [2]. Education is central to preventive medicine and prenatal care, significantly

reducing health disparities among vulnerable populations [2]. In Iraq, maternal and neonatal mortality rates remain alarmingly high. The maternal mortality ratio was recorded at 84 per 100,000 live births, while the neonatal mortality rate was 23 per 1,000 live births in 2010 [3]. To address this issue, prenatal care should ideally begin early in pregnancy or before conception [4]. The World Health Organization (WHO) recommends a minimum of four antenatal visits during pregnancy, incorporating essential interventions such as identifying and managing obstetric complications (e.g., preeclampsia), tetanus toxoid immunization, screening for infections like HIV and syphilis, and promoting optimal pregnancy spacing

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[5,6]. Antenatal care also encourages skilled birth attendance, breastfeeding, early postnatal care, and maternal health education [6]. In Iraq, maternity care services are provided across all levels of the healthcare system [3]. Skilled birth attendants, including midwives, doctors, and nurses, are trained to manage normal pregnancies and childbirth while identifying complications for timely intervention [6]. Community involvement is crucial in antenatal care utilization, as support from family members, particularly male partners and mothers-in-law, can enhance adherence to antenatal recommendations and improve maternal and neonatal outcomes [6]. Additionally, targeted interventions for unsupported pregnant women, particularly adolescents, are essential to ensure equitable access to healthcare services [6]. Community health workers play a vital role in identifying pregnant women, providing counseling on healthy lifestyles, birth planning, and linking them to healthcare services [6]. Despite improvements in prenatal care access, maternal and infant mortality disparities persist due to factors such as poverty, limited healthcare access, environmental hazards, stress, and cultural beliefs [2]. Healthcare providers must design tailored prenatal health education programs, particularly for medically indigent and illiterate pregnant women, to improve health outcomes [2]. Evaluating the quality of antenatal care is essential for identifying gaps and optimizing services to support maternal well-being and fetal health [7]. Antenatal care should also provide emotional support and guidance to women and their families, facilitating a smooth transition to parenthood [8]. The aim of this study is to evaluate the level of health awareness among pregnant women regarding prenatal care and to identify the primary sources of health information for pregnant women attending PHCCs in Baghdad Al-Russafa Health Directorate.

Methods

A descriptive cross-sectional study was conducted.

Study Setting

The study was carried out in Baghdad/Al-Russafa Health Directorate, specifically in four Primary Health Care Centers (PHCCs):

1. Al-Dubbat Specialized Family Health Center
2. Al-Mustansyria Specialized Family Health Center
3. Al-Karada Al-Sharqia PHCC
4. 1st Baghdad Al-Jadida PHCC

Study Duration

The study was conducted over four months, from January 2014 to April 2014.

Population and Sample Size

A total of 200 pregnant women who attended the selected PHCCs in Baghdad/Al-Russafa were included in the study.

Inclusion Criteria

All pregnant women who attended any of the selected PHCCs during the study period were eligible for inclusion.

Exclusion Criteria

Pregnant women in their first or second trimester without previous childbirth (primigravida) were excluded from the study.

Ethical Considerations

The study was approved by the ethical and scientific committee of the Iraqi Ministry of Health and the Council of Arab Board of Health Specialties. Informed consent was obtained from all participants before answering the questionnaire.

Data Collection

The data collection tool was a structured questionnaire designed based on international guidelines, adapted from a review of the literature, and supervised by senior experts in the Department of Community Medicine at Al-Kindy College of Medicine and the Gynecology Department. The questionnaire covered:

- **Socio-demographic characteristics** (age, education, occupation, residence, family size, house size).
- **Obstetric characteristics** (age at marriage, gestational age, number of children).
- **PHCC visit details** (frequency of visits, vaccination status, nutrition, morning sickness, rest and physical activity, birth spacing, smoking, breast care, awareness about pregnancy, delivery, and postpartum care).

Statistical Analysis

Data were analyzed using the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) version 18. Categorical variables were expressed as frequencies and percentages, while continuous variables were presented as means \pm standard deviation (SD). A p-value \leq 0.05 was considered statistically significant.

Study Limitations

The study was limited to Al-Russafa due to logistical constraints. Additionally, time limitations restricted the sample collection period.

Results

The overall mean age of pregnant women was 29.22 ± 6.31 years, while the mean age of their partners was 34.72 ± 8.64 years. Regarding education, 40.5% of mothers and 36.0% of their partners had completed secondary school. In terms of occupational status, the majority of mothers (54.0%) and partners (48.0%) were employed in the government sector. Concerning knowledge of necessary laboratory tests during pregnancy, the majority of pregnant women were aware of hemoglobin (93.0%) and urine examination (93.0%). However, awareness of screening for hepatitis B and C (3.5%) and syphilis (1.5%) was notably low. As in table 1.

Table 1: Pregnant Women and Partners Data

Category	Pregnant Women	Partners
Mean Age (Years)	29.22 ± 6.31	34.72 ± 8.64
Education (Secondary School)	40.5%	36.0%
Governmental Employment	54.0%	48.0%
Knowledge of Lab Tests		
Knowledge of HB & Urine Exam	93.0%	-
Knowledge of HBV & HCV	3.50%	-
Knowledge of Syphilis Test	1.50%	-

Table 2 shows the distribution of pregnant women by residence, family member, house size, number of children, age at marriage and gestational age.

Table 2: Distribution of Pregnant Women by Residence, Family Member, House Size, Number of Children, Age at Marriage and Gestational Time

Variable	Frequency (%)
Residence	
Urban area	183 (91.5%)
Rural area	17 (8.5%)
Total	200 (100.0)
Family member	
Two members	72 (36.0%)
3-4 members	73 (36.5%)
5-6 members	28 (14.0%)
≥ 7 members	27 (13.5%)
Total	200 (100.0)
Number of children	
No children	65 (32.5%)
One child	45 (22.5%)
2-3 children	36 (18.0%)
> 3 children	36 (18.0%)
Still birth	18 (9.0%)
Total	200 (100.0)
House size	
Two rooms	73 (36.5%)
Three rooms	100 (50.0%)
Four rooms	18 (9.0%)
> four rooms	9 (4.5%)
Total	200 (100.0)
Age at marriage	
< 20 years	36 (18.0%)
20-24 years	79 (39.5%)
25-29 years	56 (28.0%)
≥ 30 years	29 (14.5%)
Total	200 (100.0)
Gestational age	
4-12 weeks	9 (4.5%)
13-20 weeks	63 (31.5%)
21-28 weeks	64 (32.0%)
> 28 weeks	55 (27.5%)
I do not know	9 (4.5%)
Total	200 (100.0)

Table 3 presents the distribution of pregnant women based on their knowledge of vaccines during pregnancy. **77.0%** of pregnant women were aware that vaccines are needed during pregnancy, while **66.2%** specifically recognized the importance of the tetanus

vaccine. However, **45.0%** were unaware of the required number of tetanus vaccine doses, and an equal proportion (**45.0%**) believed that the tetanus vaccine provides immunity to both the mother and child.

Table 3: Pregnant Women Knowledge about Taking Vaccine during Pregnancy

Variable	Frequency (%)	P value
Do you know vaccines you need to take during pregnancy		
Yes	154 (77.0)	<0.001*
No	46 (23.0)	
Total	200 (100.0)	
Do you know the type of vaccine you need to take during pregnancy		
Tetanus vaccine	102 (66.2)	<0.001*
Measles vaccine	20 (13.0)	
Other	32 (20.8)	
Total	154 (100.0)	
Do you know No. of Tetanus vaccine you need to take during pregnancy		
< 5 doses	30 (15.0)	<0.001*
5 doses	30 (15.0)	
Only during pregnancy	50 (25.0)	
I do not know	90 (45.0)	

Table 4 illustrates pregnant women's dietary knowledge. (91.0%) of pregnant women realise they require a particular diet. (37.4%) of pregnant women realise they need carbs. 72.5% of pregnant women realise they need extra food. (40.5%) of pregnant

women realise they need more than three meals. Pregnant women realise they need vitamins and minerals (76.0%). (54.5%) of pregnant women realise they need iron. (27.5%) of pregnant women got information from physicians.

Table 4: Knowledge of Pregnant Women about Nutrition

Variable	Frequency (%)	P value
Do know that mother need special diet during pregnancy		
Yes	182 (91.0)	<0.001*
No	18 (9.0)	
Total	200 (100.0)	
Which type of food the pregnant women need?		
Carbohydrate	7 (3.8)	<0.001*
Protein	12 (6.5)	
Fruit	68(37.4)	
Vegetables	55(30.3)	
Dairy product	40 (22.0)	
Total	182 (100.0)	
Do you know that pregnant women need more meal?		
Yes	145 (72.5)	<0.001*
No	55 (27.5)	
Total	200 (100.0)	
How many meals do you need per day?		
< 3 meals	35 (17.5)	<0.001*
3 meals	84 (42.0)	
> 3 meals	81 (40.5)	
Total	200 (100.0)	

Do you know the pregnant women recommended to take vitamins and minerals? Yes No Total	 132 (66.0) 68 (34.0) 200 (100.0)	<0.001*
Which type of vitamins and minerals you should take? Iron Calcium Folic acid Vitamins Total	 72 (54.5) 7 (5.3) 17 (12.9) 36 (27.3) 132 (100.0)	<0.001*
What the source of your information about food during pregnancy? Doctors Medical staff Mother/ sister Mother in law other Total	 55 (27.5) 37 (18.5) 53 (26.5) 45 (22.5) 10 (5.0) 200 (100.0)	<0.001*

Note: *p value ≤ 0.05 is significant

Table 5 shows knowledge of pregnant women about morning sickness. (64.0%) of pregnant women has morning sickness. (41.4%) of pregnant women complain from nausea and vomiting. (53.1%) of

pregnant women overcome morning sickness by small snacks. (54.0%) of pregnant women did not complain from constipation. (58.7%) of pregnant women overcome constipation by increase fluid intake.

Table 5: Knowledge of Pregnant Women about Morning Sickness

Variable	Frequency (%)	P value
Do you have morning sickness? Yes No Total	 128 (64.0) 72 (36.0) 200 (100.0)	<0.001*
Which sign and symptom you complain? Loss of appetite Increase appetite Nausea and vomiting Taste unusual things Total	 22 (17.2) 46 (35.9) 53 (41.4) 7 (5.5) 128 (100.0)	<0.001*
How to overcome this complain? Small snacks Stop taking certain food Taking varied food Medication Nothing Total	 68 (53.1) 18 (14.1) 27 (21.1) 4 (3.1) 11 (8.6) 128 (100.0)	<0.001*
Do you complain from constipation during pregnancy? Yes No Total	 92 (46.0) 108 (54.0) 200 (100.0)	<0.001*
What do you do if you complain from constipation? Drink fluid Increase fibers intake Both of them No one Total	 54 (58.7) 24 (26.08) 4 (4.35) 10 (10.87) 92 (100.0)	<0.001*

Note: *p value ≤ 0.05 is significant

Table 6 shows the knowledge of pregnant women about rest and physical activity. (59.5%) of pregnant

women sleep eight hours per day. (2.5%) of pregnant women adapted physical activity during pregnancy.

Table 6: Knowledge of Pregnant Women about Rest and Physical Activity

Variable	Frequency (%)	P value
How many hours you sleep per day during pregnancy?		<0.001*
< 8 hours	54 (27.0)	
8 hours	119 (59.5)	
> 8 hours	27 (13.5)	
Total	200 (100.0)	
Did you adapt physical activity during pregnancy?		<0.001*
Yes	5 (2.5)	
No	195 (97.5)	
Total	200 (100.0)	
Which type of physical activity did you adapt?		<0.001*
Jogging	1 (20.0)	
Walking	4 (80.0)	
Swimming	0 (0.0)	
Pelvic floor exercise	0 (0.0)	
Total	5 (100.0)	

Note: *p value ≤ 0.05 is significant

Table 7 shows the knowledge of pregnant women about distance between gestations. (55.0%) of pregnant women think that the perfect distance between pregnancies is two years. (18.0%) of pregnant women adapted IUD for family planning. (41.0%) of

pregnant women get the advice about family planning from doctors. (50.0%) of pregnant women think that the suitable age of getting pregnancy is between 21-24 years old.

Table 7: Knowledge of Pregnancy Women about Distance between Gestations

Variable	Frequency (%)	P value
Do you know the perfect distance between gestations?		<0.001*
< 1 year	36 (18.0)	
> 1 year	54 (27.0)	
> 2 years	110 (55.0)	
Total	200 (100.0)	
What you adapted for family planning?		<0.001*
Breast feeding	23 (11.5)	
OCP	27 (13.5)	
IUD	36 (18.0)	
Using condom	26 (13.0)	
Not used	18 (9.0)	
Injection contraceptive	30 (15.0)	
Other (withdrawal , rhythm,....)	40 (20.0)	
Total	200 (100.0)	
Whose gave you the advice about family planning?		<0.001*
Doctors	82 (41.0)	
Medical staff	45 (22.5)	
Mother/ sister	36 (18.0)	
Mother in law	28 (14.0)	
Other	9 (4.5)	
Total	200 (100.0)	

Do you know the suitable age of getting pregnancy?		
15 years	27 (13.5)	<0.001*
16-20 years	28 (14.0)	
21-24 years	100 (50.0)	
25-29 years	27 (13.5)	
30-34 years	18 (9.0)	
35-39 years	0 (0.0)	
Total	200 (100.0)	

Note: *p value ≤ 0.05 is significant:

Table 8 shows the knowledge of pregnant women about smoking during pregnancy. (82.5%) of pregnant women know that smoking affects pregnancy. (40.0%)

of pregnant women know that smoking may causes congenital anomalies.

Table 8: Knowledge of Pregnant Women about Smoking during Pregnancy

Variable	Frequency (%)	P value
Do you know that the smoking effects on pregnancy?		
Yes	165 (82.5)	<0.001*
No	35 (17.5)	
Total	200 (100.0)	
What are the effect of smoking on pregnancy?		
Congenital anomalies	66 (40.0)	<0.001*
Failure to thrive	43 (26.0)	
Abortion/ Prematurity	30 (18.3)	
Mother’s respiratory problems	18 (10.9)	
Cancers	8 (4.8)	
Total	165 (100.0)	

Note: *p value ≤ 0.05 is significant

Table 9 shows the knowledge of pregnant women about breast care. (7.0%) of pregnant women care their breasts by cleaning nipple. (58.5%) of pregnant women feed their children only from breast. (42.5%) of

pregnant women know that the duration of breast feeding is six months. (41.0%) of pregnant women their source about breast feeding is doctors.

Table 9: Knowledge of Pregnant Women about Breast Care

Variable	Frequency (%)	P value
How do you care your breast?		
By cleaning nipple	14 (7.0)	<0.001*
By self exam	74 (37)	
By manual emptying	5 (2.5)	
By breast feed child	77 (38.5)	
Wearing suitable bra	30 (15)	
Total	200 (100.0)	
Which of child feeding you adapted?		
Only breast feeding	117 (58.5)	<0.001*
Bottle feeding	38 (19.0)	
Both	45 (22.5)	
Total	200 (100.0)	
Do you know the duration of breast feeding?		
< 6 months	85 (42.5)	<0.001*
6-12 months	75 (37.5)	
> 1 year	40 (20.0)	
Total	200 (100.0)	

Whose you source about breastfeeding?		<0.001*
Doctors	82 (41.0)	
Medical staff	45 (22.5)	
Mother/ sister	36 (18.0)	
Mother in law	28 (14.0)	
Other	9 (4.5)	
Total	200 (100.0)	

Note: *p value ≤ 0.05 is significant

Table 10 shows knowledge of pregnant women about delivery. (57.5%) of pregnant women knew the signs of delivery that need urgent going to hospital, from them (51.3%) named it as uterine bleeding. (72.0%) of pregnant women found that hospital is suitable place

for delivery. (82.2%) found delivery by TBA is suitable if at home. (51.5%) of pregnant women knew the signs of delivery, from them (33.0%) named it as uterine contraction.

Table 10: Knowledge of Pregnant Women about Pregnancy and Delivery

Variable	Frequency (%)	P value
Do you know danger signs during pregnancy?		<0.001*
Yes	115 (57.5)	
No	85 (42.5)	
Total	200 (100.0)	
What are these danger signs during pregnancy?		<0.001*
vaginal bleeding	59 (51.3)	
severe headache with blurred of vision	38 (33.0)	
Severe abdominal pain	18 (15.7)	
fever	0 (0.00)	
Total	115 (100.0)	
What is the suitable place for delivery?		<0.001*
Hospital	144 (72.0)	
Home delivery	56 (28.0)	
Total	200 (100.0)	
By whom, if delivered at home?		<0.001*
TBA	46 (82.2)	
Midwife	5 (8.9)	
Both	5 (8.9)	
Total	56 (100.0)	
Do you know the sings of delivery?		<0.001*
Yes	103 (51.5)	
No	97 (48.5)	
Total	200 (100.0)	
What are the sings of delivery?		<0.001*
Bloody sticky discharge	34 (33.0)	
Painful contraction	42 (40.7)	
Water have broken	27 (26.3)	
Total	103 (100.0)	

Note: *p value ≤ 0.05 is significant

Table 11 shows knowledge of pregnant women about postpartum period.

Table 11: Knowledge of Pregnant Women about Postpartum Period

Variable	Frequency (%)	P value
Do you know how many PHC visit during postpartum period?		<0.001*
One visit	36 (18.0)	
Two visits	36 (18.0)	

No need I do not know Total	81 (40.5) 47 (23.5) 200 (100.0)	
Do you know the time of first visit during postpartum period? One week 4- 6 weeks I do not know Total	 60 (30.0) 75 (37.5) 65 (32.5) 200 (100.0)	<0.001*
Do you know signs than need urgent going to hospital during postpartum? Yes No Total	 129 (64.5) 71 (35.5) 200 (100.0)	<0.001*
Do you know signs than need urgent going to hospital during postpartum? Sever vaginal bleeding Convulsion Severe abdominal pain Difficult breathing Fever Total	 78 (60.5) 23 (17.8) 16 (12.4) 7 (5.4) 5 (3.9) 129 (100.0)	<0.001*
Do you know the duration of taking fero -folic after delivery? Three months > three months I do not know No need Total	 45 (22.5) 45 (22.5) 65 (32.5) 45 (22.5) 200 (100.0)	<0.001*

Note: *p value ≤ 0.05 is significant

Discussion

This study assessed the level of health awareness among pregnant women attending PHCCs in Baghdad Al-Russafa and identified their sources of information. The mean age of pregnant women in this study was 29.22 ± 6.31 years, with the majority (91.5%) residing in urban areas. Most women had completed secondary education (40.5%) and were employed (54.0%). These findings were similar to studies conducted in Ethiopia [9] and Saudi Arabia [10], where education and employment rates were comparable. Obstetric data showed that 32.5% of participants had no children, while 9.0% had a history of stillbirth. The majority (39.5%) were married at 20-24 years, and most women (32.0%) sought antenatal care at 21-28 weeks. These findings align with studies from Arbil [11] and Ethiopia [12], where late gestational age attendance was also common. A significant proportion (48.0%) initiated their first antenatal visit in the second trimester, similar to findings from Bangladesh [13] and Ethiopia [9]. Many women delayed ANC due to a lack of awareness or perceived absence of pregnancy-related problems. The study found that 60.0% of participants were unaware that the first ANC visit should occur in the first trimester, consistent with studies from Uganda [14,15].

Additionally, only 7.0% recognized the importance of screening for hepatitis B and syphilis, reflecting low awareness, similar to findings from Tanzania [16]. Awareness of vaccines needed during pregnancy was moderate, with 77.0% knowing about vaccination, but only 66.2% correctly identifying TT as the essential vaccine. Additionally, 57.9% lacked knowledge about the required TT doses, similar to findings in Pakistan [17]. This suggests a need for more educational efforts on immunization. While 91.0% of participants acknowledged the need for a special diet during pregnancy, only 37.4% and 30.3% identified fruits and vegetables as essential, while carbohydrate intake was largely neglected (3.8%). These results align with studies from Ethiopia [18] and Pakistan [19], where nutritional knowledge was also inadequate. Only 66.0% were aware of the need for vitamins and minerals, with iron and folic acid being the most commonly recognized supplements. This limited knowledge was also observed in studies from Bangladesh [13] and Saudi Arabia [10]. The prevalence of morning sickness was 64.0%, with nausea and vomiting being the most common complaints. Similar findings were reported in studies from Tanzania [20] and Saudi Arabia [21]. However, awareness of managing morning sickness

was limited. Additionally, 46.0% reported constipation, but only 4.3% increased fiber intake, showing low awareness, similar to findings from the UK [22].

A majority (59.5%) of pregnant women slept at least 8 hours daily, but 97.5% did not engage in physical activity. The few who did preferred walking (80.0%). These results align with findings from Zambia [23], where 74% of participants lacked knowledge about exercise during pregnancy. Most participants (55.0%) preferred more than two years between pregnancies, demonstrating good awareness, consistent with studies in Ethiopia [24]. The most commonly used contraceptive methods were withdrawal (20.0%) and IUDs (18.0%), differing from findings in Egypt [25] and Saudi Arabia [26], where oral contraceptives were preferred. Doctors and medical staff were the primary sources of family planning advice (41.0%). Awareness of smoking's harmful effects was high (82.5%), with congenital anomalies (40.0%) being the most recognized consequence, consistent with studies from Jordan [27] and India [28]. Regarding breast care, 38.5% received advice on breast care, and 37.0% on breastfeeding. Most (58.5%) initiated breastfeeding immediately after delivery, while 37.5% continued for only 6-12 months. These results are in line with studies from Saudi Arabia [10] and England [29]. Knowledge of danger signs during pregnancy was moderate (57.5%), with vaginal bleeding being the most recognized (51.3%), similar to findings from Ethiopia [12]. Hospital delivery was preferred by 72.0% of participants, with safety being the primary reason. Home deliveries were mainly attended by traditional birth attendants (82.2%), consistent with study from Syria [30]. Postnatal care knowledge was low, with 40.5% believing that postnatal visits were unnecessary, similar to findings from Saudi Arabia [31]. Only 64.5% recognized at least one postpartum danger sign, with severe vaginal bleeding being the most identified (60.4%), aligning with studies from Bangladesh [32]. Knowledge of iron and folic acid supplementation postpartum was also low (32.5%).

Conclusion

Overall, this study highlights gaps in antenatal care awareness, vaccination, nutrition, physical activity, and postpartum care among pregnant women. Strengthening health education efforts through PHCCs and family involvement is crucial to improving maternal and neonatal health outcomes.

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